

Stanford International Mars Mission

Sections by Kurt Schwehr
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2.1.2 Mars Surface Science

(sections on Weather by David Chappell)

This is a quick summary of some of the major science questions that can be explored while on the martian surface. It includes objectives suitable for both human and robotic exploration. This list is a cross between goals of the Stanford International Mars Mission (SIMM) and a variety of published sources. (Ref. Carr and Pepin 1992, CNES 1992, Greeley 1990, Stoker 1989, Carr 1981, etc.) The objectives are summarized in Table 2.1.2-1.

- **Exo-Biology:**
 - Complex organic molecules
 - Presence of micro-fossils in sedimentary rocks
 - Presence and distribution of extant life
- **Geology:**
 - Evolution and processes of polar caps
 - Formation of the valley networks
 - Northern lowlands/Southern highlands dichotomy
 - Paleontology should fossils exist
 - Stratigraphy - dating of rock units and aerological events
 - Surface mineralogy, morphology, and processes
 - Volcanic history and present activity (geothermal)
 - Volatile history - sources and sinks of H₂O, CO₂, N₂
- **Geophysics:**
 - Global and local magnetic fields - present and past Planetary interior, structure and processes
 - Tectonics - Marsquakes and the cause of the Tharsis bulge
 - Thermal history, heat flow, and temperature gradient
- **Meteorology:**
 - Atmosphere - origin, history, mass, and dynamics
 - Climate history
 - Dust storms

SURFACE SCIENCE OBJECTIVES
TABLE 2.1.2-1

2.1.2.1 Exo-biology

Exobiology is perhaps the most important goal of Mars exploration, leading with the question: Is there life on Mars and if it is not there now, was life ever present. A major focus of pre-human (precursor) missions should be the search for extant life and prebiological molecules, since the arrival of major organic contaminants from Earth will bring compounding problems to these experiments. For example, once humans arrive it may not be possible to distinguish whether humans were the source of any biological compounds. Also, if microorganisms are found, and if they are not radically different, they could actually be Earth sourced life that has mutated and evolved rapidly in the very different martian environment. Discovery of extant life would most certainly be strong grounds for postponing any manned mission.

The question of extant life is still very open, as the Viking landers have left a large number of questions unanswered. Even what is known from these two sites is difficult to extrapolate to the rest of Mars from Viking landing sites. (Ref. Don Devanchency 1-20-93) The current best guess is that the martian surface is probably dead because of four factors: there is no liquid water at the surface - the pressure and temperature are near the triple point of water, so ice and frost go directly to gas; the surface is very oxidizing; the influx of UV light is very high due to the lack of a martian ozone layer; and finally, there is relatively small amount of N₂ available for metabolic activity. (Ref. McKay, 2-1-93)

Because of this harsh environment, we have to look for places that are likely to harbor life from this world. There are several possible circumstances on Mars that may be harboring life or traces of life. One example is an area where ground ice interacts with the high thermal gradient of local volcanism. This interaction may produce stable water in the subsurface. Two other sites that may have had life in the past which could be preserved as frozen below the surface or as fossils are paleolakes and runoff channels that probably had periodic liquid water.

2.1.2.1.1 Complex Organic Molecules

There are many possible ways of looking for life. If there has been or is life, there may be remnants of complex organic molecules present that we may be able to detect. If these molecules exist on Mars, they will most likely be found preserved in a permafrost layer where they are protected from UV radiation and the heavily oxidizing surface.

2.1.2.1.2 Presence of micro-fossils in sedimentary rocks

If there was life on Mars, it is assumed that life started in a very small form and may or may not have evolved to larger, "macro", forms. Even if larger forms did not develop, it may still be possible to find remains of micro fossils. If martian organisms had any "hard parts" they may be preserved in paleo-lake, paleo-oceans, or other sedimentary environments. See Boardman et. al., 1987 for a recent work on paleontology. These hard body parts can be composed of mineralizations such as calcium carbonate, aragonite, chitin, or some metals. On Earth it took a long time to develop hard parts, as these hard parts are not seen until the

Precambrian/Cambrian boundary - approximately four billion years after the formation of the Earth. Therefore it would be prudent to focus on looking for masses of micro-biological communities that leave behind structures known as stromatolites. These are some of the first pieces of evidence of life on Earth in the Archean eon and show up about 3.5 billion years ago - one billion years after the formation of the Earth. Currently we can see stromatolites forming in two areas on the Earth: salty lagoons in Shark Bay, Australia and in perennially frozen lakes in the dry valleys of Antarctica.

2.1.2.1.3 Presence and distribution of extant life

If we detect life on Mars it will be important to gain as much knowledge as possible before we seriously contaminate it since this will only be our second view of evolution in the universe. The jump in our understanding of life would be absolutely amazing. A large number of geologists are currently working hard on Earth to understand how groups of organisms work in the present Earth environment since this information can often be used with fossils to tell us a lot about the environment in which now extinct organisms lived. This would open a vast new door to biology, beyond the table-top setups and theoretical concepts of current exobiology.

If life evolved early on in the martian environment, there is a chance that life could still be alive. One example of the hardiness of life is where pyrobacteria have been found living inside the turbine water in nuclear reactors. A better example comes from the dry valleys of Antarctica. Large mats of bacteria live at the bottom of the perennially ice covered lakes. Portions of the mat are transported up to the bottom of the ice cover where they are eventually brought to the surface of the ice over several years. The wind blows the exposed mat to a new site, where, if the bacteria find water, they start a new colony. (Ref. Andersen, 1993)

2.1.2.2 Geology

Geology is an area in which there is large amounts of work to do. It is a rapidly evolving field, that has not existed in its current form for very long. For example, plate tectonics not been in the text books for more than a decade or two. Being able to see another world will undoubtedly lead to major revolutions in thought about geologic process in a process called comparative planetology. It will be a tough job. On Earth, there have been thousands of modern geologist since the early 1900's. With Mars, were are still at the state we were at when the first geologic map of England produced in 1812: lots of well educated guesses and few solid answers. One of the most important tasks in geologic terms is to extend the set of geologic maps that cover as much area as possible and inasmuch detail as possible using ground truths to orbital observations. This section on geology includes the categories of geochemistry and mineralogy which are often separated out into their own topics. The martian geology may be able to provide resources for exploration. Materials for the production of consumables for fuel and for breathing air are present as well as other energy sources we do not yet know about. The known martian resources are water, O₂ from CO₂ and soil, Ar/N₂ for breathing, and materials for various fuels. Some may be available in the subsurface as well as from the atmosphere.

2.1.2.2.1 Evolution and processes of polar caps

Understanding the polar ice caps is extremely important for two major reasons. The layers in the ice contain an extremely valuable record of the climatic history. Ice usually has bubbles that contain trapped gasses from ancient atmospheres. Stable isotopic ratios similar to that of O16/O18 may be able to tell us about martian climate through time, although they will probably require different interpretations than measurements on Earth. Besides containing a record of the history, the polar ice caps themselves are a major control on climate. The CO₂ mass in the atmosphere is modulated by how much dry ice is stored on the caps.

2.1.2.2.2 Formation of the valley networks

The valleys on Mars were thought to have been cut by large floods of water. The sediments on the valley floors may contain fossils of critters that lived in the water. The cuts have another important feature: since they are so deep, they may provide access to very ancient rock, both sedimentary and volcanic/plutonic, that have been buried. From these exposures, we may be able to build up a more complete stratigraphic record.

We should be able to see a wide range of the sedimentary processes that occur on Mars within these valleys such as mass wasting. Canyon walls may be a good source of water. There may still be ice covered lakes on the valley floors which may be the last large scale liquid water bodies on the surface of the planet (Ref. McKay, 2-1-93). The deposits in the valley floors are an excellent site to search for fossil remains. Some of these deposits may represent lake deposits. See section 2.2.2.3.4 for a description of Valles Marineris, the largest valley on Mars.

2.1.2.2.3 Northern lowlands/Southern highlands dichotomy

The Northern lowlands, Southern highlands dichotomy is a major break in the surface features encircling the planet approximately one third of the way down from the North pole to the South pole (around 35° North). The lowlands material is much younger as seen by a much lower crater density. The cause of this break is not clear. There are a number of possible causes including: a large impact or a massive tectonic event. The North consists mainly of younger cratered and smooth plains with some ridges and domes. The South consists primarily of ancient heavily cratered highlands.

2.1.2.2.4 Paleontology

If there are fossils on Mars, it will be important to carefully collect as many as possible. With these fossils we can start to build up a progression of martian evolution. On Earth, fossils provide a valuable tool for dating sedimentary rocks from the age range of the organism as sedimentary rocks frequently do not contain material which can be radioisotope dated. This is possible only if life existed and left significant remains. Remains may still exist even if the organic material has been removed and/or replaced.

2.1.2.2.5 Stratigraphy

There are a number of scientific questions that fall under the title of stratigraphy, the sequencing and dating of rock features and events. One of the most important concerns is getting some hard numbers on the age of various features from radioisotope dating. Once a few basic ages are done, the relative ages from cratering can be put to an "absolute" time scale.

There are a number of layered deposits visible from orbit. However, as can be seen on Earth, there is a large amount of layering that is not visible from satellites because the change in properties is not observable by space born equipment or is just plain too small. Some examples are, changes in sedimentary structures like ripples or fossil progressions. As a result, a large amount of the work on stratigraphy must be done directly on the surface with direct access to features of all scales. As Mars exploration continues, we will be able to put together a continually better chronology of the events that have occurred on Mars since its formation.

2.1.2.2.6 Surface lithology, mineralogy, morphology, AND processes

Lithology, mineralogy, and morphology are some of the key clues to understanding the evolution of near surface crust. From this information, geologists can more fully understand the surface processes that occur on Mars. For example, the mineralogy around volcanoes can tell about composition and activity at great depths back in time.

2.1.2.2.7 Volcanic history and present activity

Mars shows a history of intense volcanic and tectonic activity into the past. Mars has the largest known volcano in the solar system, Olympus Mons. The volcanic areas present a window into the interior of the planet. Most of the material that erupts comes from great depths. Some may even come from the upper mantle. An example of this on the Earth are the olivine nodules that are brought to the surface in Hawaii and peridotites at the base of ocean crust sequences. The SNC meteorites found on Earth present evidence for volcanism on Mars as recently as 150 million years ago, if they are in fact actually from Mars (Ref. Carr, 2-1-93)

One of the key targets in assessing the present activity, is the search for geothermal areas. The heat combined with subsurface H₂O may provide an area of liquid water which has the possibility of harboring life.

2.1.2.2.8 Volatile history

Only a few of the volatiles present on and in Mars are visible in the atmosphere and polar caps. The volatile history is of major importance to exobiology and mineralogy interests. The rocks on Mars, in particular the layered units, can tell us what liquids and gasses were present in the past. The sequences of rocks present the opportunity to understand the cycles that operate on Mars. Correlations with Earth will be important: it will be a fantastic opportunity to tell which events were local to one of the two planets and which were massive enough to affect both

planets. Understanding what volatiles have been around is one of the best ways to gain understanding in the procession/history of the solar system.

There currently is evidence of large quantities of H₂O on Mars. The most visible evidence is the numerous instances of erosion as in the river valleys. At some meteor impact sites there is ejecta that looks like it was mud when it was thrown from the blast area. Finally, there is different morphology of surface features at the high latitudes which appear to be unstable in the same manner that features on Earth that are laden with ice deform. The suspicion is that most of the water is in the old cratered terrain. (Ref. Carr, 2-1-93)

2.1.2.3 Geophysics

Since we have no way to directly look directly into the center of a planet, we have to resort to geophysical techniques to give us information on those hard to reach places.

2.1.2.3.1 Global and local magnetic fields

The global magnetic field can give us two kinds of information: the structure of mantle/core motion and time histories of surface rocks that contain magnetic minerals. Currently, Mars has a magnetic field that is in the neighborhood of 10⁻⁴ times the value at Earth (Table 2.1.2.3.1-1.) The field is extremely weak and it is debated whether there exists a field at all. The motion of the mantle or core is the only easy explanation for large planetary magnetic fields. Traces of the planetary field are often saved in rocks that contain magnetic minerals as these rocks form. If there was a large field in Mars' past, it will be important to look for magnetic reversals. If they occurred, these patterns represents an important tool for correlating ages of rock units. Once the large scale reversals are mapped and dated, reversals combined with other information give a better picture of when a sequence of events occurred. The magnetic field can also be used to determine at what latitude that the rocks were deposited.

	Earth	Mars
Field at equator	35-40x10 ³ nT	30 nT
Dipole moment	8x10 ¹⁵ Tm ³	<2x10 ¹² Tm ³

MAGNETIC FIELDS TABLE 2.1.2.3.1-1

2.1.2.3.2 Planetary interior - structure and processes

It is important to understand the interior of Mars to work on our theories for the evolution of the solar system. We still do not know what the internal structure is beyond the mean density and volume of the planet. Therefore we can only guess. We would like to know if there ever was plate tectonics on Mars. If there is, why did it stop; otherwise why did plate tectonics not occur?

The available data on Mars are so limited that we can not confirm the existence of internal structures such as a core, mantle, and asthenosphere that are seen within the Earth, while the thickness of the crust has yet to be determined. Several models have been constructed of the internal state of the planet, but they make a number of assumptions about information that is known for the Earth but not Mars. An example of the range of results from the different models is that current estimates of the core range from 1/3 to 1/2 of the radius of Mars depending on what is assumed to be the material content of the core. (Ref. MARSNET, 1992)

2.1.2.3.3 Tectonics

Currently we are limited to seismic data from one of the Viking landers, Viking 2, which had large problems with noise. From this data, we have one possible marsquake recorded. Recently, it has been predicted from orbital photos that there are marsquakes. Marsquakes give an indication of the stress that the crust is under and allow the interior of the planet to be imaged.

A probable source for a good number of Marsquakes, if they occur, is the Tharsis region. This whole area is a large bulge that encompasses a set of massive volcanoes. The major question is what is the cause of the bulge and how is it remaining stable or whether it is stable. Is it isostatically held up or is there an upwelling of low density mantle material? The other main source of seismic activity is probably the occasional meteorite impact. Mars is expected to be more seismically active than the Moon. It has been predicted that marsquakes up to magnitude three should be common with occasional quakes up to magnitude five on the Richter scale (Ref. Trall, Golumbek, and Banerdt, 1992.)

2.1.2.3.4 Thermal history, heat flow, and temperature gradient

Heat flow measurements and temperature gradient knowledge will allow better prediction of the internal state of the planet. Using this data will allow a more accurate depiction of the temperature history of the interior of Mars.

2.1.2.4 Meteorology

The atmosphere of Mars is much thinner than that of Earth, yet it is quite active meteorologically. Our current knowledge of the Martian weather comes primarily from the two Viking landers in the Northern hemisphere and three orbiters (Mariner 9, Viking 1 and 2). Theoretical meteorology has had considerable success with Mars. With the exception of dust storms, Martian weather can be predicted. See Michael Carr's *The Surface of Mars*, 1981 for more details on martian meteorology.

2.1.2.4.1 Atmosphere

The atmosphere of Mars is quite different from that of Earth. The martian atmosphere is primarily composed of carbon dioxide, with nitrogen and argon as secondary components. Table

2.1.2.4.1-1 lists the abundances as measured by the Viking landers. As on Earth, convection is the prime mechanism that drives the martian atmosphere.

Component	Percent
Carbon Dioxide (CO ²)	95.3
Nitrogen (N ²)	2.7
Argon (Ar)	1.6
Oxygen (O ²)	0.15
Water (H ² O)	0.03
Neon (Ne)	0.0003

ATMOSPHERIC COMPOSITION TABLE 2.1.2.4.1-1

Both the pressure and temperature on Mars are much lower than on Earth. The surface pressure on Mars is about six millibars (0.006 atm), with maximum and minimum values of 8.9 and 1 millibars. An arbitrary "sea level" has been chosen where the pressure is 6.1 millibars. The recorded surface temperature ranges from 140 to 295 K. The Viking landing sites averaged 210 K (-63 C), while daily variations were 190 to 240 K. The typical temperature is below 0 C, but in some equatorial regions the temperature may climb above freezing.

Water vapor is only a minor component of the atmosphere because temperatures are almost always well below the freezing point. The Viking orbiters found that the amount of water vapor varies by season and location. Water vapor on Earth is more than 200 times the amount measured on Mars. Nevertheless, the atmosphere is almost saturated with water, evidenced by the frost seen at the Viking landing sites. The low pressure and temperature keep the atmosphere from holding much water.

The Martian atmosphere is generally clearer than that of Earth, with many fewer clouds, but several types of clouds form in the atmosphere of Mars. These include white water ice clouds, yellow carbon-dioxide clouds, and dust clouds (see Section 2.1.2.4.3). The water ice clouds are similar to those in the Earth's atmosphere. They often form around mountains, and low-lying H₂O fog is also possible when the temperature is very low - just before sunrise. The canyons, such as Candor Chasma, may experience this morning fog. At high altitudes, the CO₂ in the atmosphere can condense to form hazes of dry ice crystals.

The winter and summer weather patterns are quite different. The huge temperature difference between the equator and the winter pole dominates the winter hemisphere. Brisk westerly winds and strong low-pressure areas result. Cyclonic storms are common near the pole as winter

approaches. The thin martian atmosphere allows more sunlight to reach the summer pole than on Earth. As a result, weather in the summer hemisphere is more stable with prevailing easterly winds. Dominant summer wind systems are caused by the expansion and contraction of the atmosphere as a result of daily solar heating. Wind speeds of 10 m/s are not uncommon. Surface winds are dominated by early morning downslope and afternoon upslope winds. There are also winds associated with the terminator.

2.1.2.4.2 Climate history

Evidence from channels indicates that Mars may once have had large amounts of surface water. The presence of liquid water implies that the climate was different at such a time. Furthermore, the layering of the polar regions suggests that Mars may undergo climatic changes similar to the ice ages on Earth with a cycle on the order of ten-thousand years. There also seem to be longer term trends. Several billion years ago, temperatures were warmer, the atmosphere was thicker, there may have been a greenhouse effect, and rain may have fallen. In those early days, the martian atmosphere more closely resembled that on Earth, and it would have been more favorable to the development of life.

Due to its small size (compared to Earth) and greater distance from the Sun, Mars eventually cooled and lost much of its atmosphere. The small gravity of Mars was unable to hold in lighter molecules of gas, and escape of the atmosphere gradually lowered the temperature. It eventually became cold enough that water froze out of the atmosphere, thus further reducing the atmosphere's ability to retain heat. This loss of atmosphere probably took place within a few hundred million years. Evidence from runoff channels indicates that rain probably has not fallen on Mars for at least three billion years. The result of these climatic changes is the cold, dry planet of today.

2.1.2.4.3 Dust storms

Another major feature of the Martian weather is dust clouds that are raised by winds. Modern analysis reveals that the channels (sometimes misnamed canals) first seen by Giovanni Schiaparelli were actually patterns of dust clouds. These clouds can grow to cover a large fraction of the surface. Storms are common all over the planet. For example, 35 individual storms were seen on Mars in 1977, two of which developed into global storms. Various locations have different frequencies of dust storms. Candor Chasma, for example, has been seen to have a moderate number of storms.

Major dust storms occur in the southern hemisphere summer. They usually develop after Mars passes perihelion, but they can occur at any time. These storms seem to feed upon themselves as they grow. The dust storms spread outward across the surface and carry more and more dust high into the atmosphere.

The storms can occasionally envelop the entire planet with a featureless haze. During such periods, the dust clouds absorb most of the sunlight before it reaches the surface, and the

atmosphere is heated from above. The troposphere disappears, planet wide temperatures tend to become uniform, and atmospheric circulation changes. After a month or two, the dust settles out, and the atmosphere returns to its normal status.

Besides being a strictly scientific interest, martian dust storms present a hazard at worst and an annoyance at best to many Mars missions. Of particular interest is the dangers it poses to a manned presence on the surface of Mars.

The most likely problem is with communication. Dust will almost certainly block out any optical communications links. What is not obvious, is the potential for the dust to block out the radio frequency transmissions. If the dust has a lot of iron in it, it may act in the same way that metal chaff does towards radar signals - seriously disrupting any signals that pass through the dust. If this is the case, the base can be equipped with a ELF system which should be to get through the dust, the tradeoff being a much lower bandwidth resulting in a lower data rate.

One problem is with fine particles in the atmosphere that can electrically charge a surface they contact. This is a hazard with helicopters on Earth, as friction on the vehicle's surface builds up a very large charge. One other possible charge source is from triboluminescence of clay particles under very low atmospheric pressures. A discharge has the potential to damage a suit or other sensitive equipment.

Simulations and field studies have given a base line that needs to be compared to the actual martian conditions before the arrival of humans. Under Mars like conditions, agitated sand has produced potentials of up to 5 kV/m (Ref. Heonig, 1975). The primary causes of charging are: contact electrification, frictional electrification, piezoelectric charges, and cleavage electrification (Ref. Greeley, 1978). Under the low martian pressure it is much easier to get arcing from these charges, so this could be a serious problem.

The final problem with dust storms is sand-blasting of exposed surfaces. It has been predicted that on Mars sand grains will begin saltating in about 25 to 30 m/s winds (Ref. Greeley, 1980). These grains will impact on any exposed surface within a meter or two of the surface. If winds are below this start up speed, then this will probably not be a concern.

2.2.2.3 Precursor Rover Mission Options

2.2.2.3.1 Goal

This section describes two missions that fit the 1998 and 2000 launch windows to Mars which currently have no scheduled flights. They could provide continuity to the Mars exploration plan. The second mission works well with the SIMM precursor missions in that it provides much needed context for human surface exploration. These two options are meant only as a small sampling of what could be done within these two launch windows using existing technology. All of the landing site numbers mentioned refer to the Mars Landing Site Catalog (Ref. Greeley, 1990).

2.2.2.3.2 Rover system, assumptions, and constraints

The rover that looks the most attractive for these missions is the Russian Marsokhod described in Appendix A.1. It should be outfitted with a laser-rangefinder, mass spectrometer, core drill, panoramic camera with zoom, ground penetrating radar, and basic meteorology instruments. Several of the missions will substitute/add instruments to suit the objectives. The first two rovers are sent on the highest priority missions so that if one of the first two rovers should fail, one of the next two rovers can be retargeted to replace the damaged rover. The lander should be equipped with a descent imager to give the best context to the rover mission and allow for improvements in the mission plan. Once down, the lander should deploy a seismometer to add to the global network started by the NASA MESUR and ESA MARSNET missions. None of these missions are meant to be sample returns due to cost considerations. During each launch window, two Marsokhods will be launched on a Proton or similarly capable launch vehicle.

2.2.2.3.3 Option A - General Science

The goal of this mission set is to gain a wide spectrum of knowledge about very different sites scattered about the planet.

2.2.2.3.3.1 1998 Launch Window

These two rovers are targeted for sites in the southern hemisphere of Mars.

2.2.2.3.3.1.1 Biological Mission

The target for this exobiology mission is a high latitude permafrost/ground ice area. The exact site is to be determined by Mars Observer imaging. The ideal site would be above 70 degrees South latitude in an area of a paleo-lake. The reason for choosing the southern hemisphere is due to the Northern lowlands being much younger - probably only one or two billion years old. The processes that created the lowlands probably destroyed signs of previous life.

2.2.2.3.3.1.2 Sedimentology and volcanology mission

This mission is to a small channel named Dao Valles in Hadriaca Patera. The canyon is approximately 200 km long. The site area is listed as site #32 and is near sites #49, #62, and #80 (Ref. Greeley, 1990). The rover should land near the top of the canyon and progress down the valley. It is assumed to be easier to travel down a surface than it is to go up. For example, sliding down is often possible where a vehicle is not able to climb.

2.2.2.3.3.2 2000 Launch Window

2.2.2.3.3.2.1 Volcanology mission

The target is a small volcano named Uranus Tholus. It is an older volcano located on the Tharsis Bulge at 26N 97W. The rover is to land near the base of the volcano and traverse towards the caldera. The smaller size of the volcano allows the rover to traverse a larger number of volcanic facies within its mission range. A rover around Olympus Mons for example would not be able to get close to more than three or four features since they are so large compared to the 100 km range of the rover.

The landing site is 10 to 20 km West of Uranus Tholus at an elevation of about 4500 meters. The vehicle will then traverse East, upwards to the caldera. The highest elevation of the edge of the caldera is approximately 8500 m.

2.2.2.3.3.2 Backup/Opportunity mission

If the backup and opportunity missions are not needed, this rover could be sent to one of many interesting sites: Olympus Mons (sites number 28 and 36) or Elysium Mons (site 40) both of which are young volcanoes, or a major impact crater.

2.2.2.3.4 Option B - Human precursor

The largest valley system is Valles Marineris. It contains Candor Chasma which is the proposed primary landing site for SIMM's first manned landing. Carr (1981) described Valles Marineris from the Viking missions data:

"Just south of the equator... are several enormous, interconnected canyons, which have been collectively called Valles Marineris. They extend roughly east-west for over 4,000 km, from the summit of the Tharsis bulge at Noctis Labyrinthus, down the crest of a broad rise on the eastern flank of the bulge, to some low-lying areas of chaotic terrain between Chryse Planitia and Margaritifer Sinus. Individual canyons may be over 200 km wide and 7 km deep. In the central section, where there are three partly connected parallel canyons, the entire system is over 700 km across. ... The canyons are poorly graded and are commonly choked with landslide debris, and most of them lack indications of fluvial action on their floors [that are seen in the channels.] Many sections are segmented and consist of strings of closed depressions rather than a continuous canyon."

"The canyons can be divided into three sections: a complex maze of interconnected canyons-- the Noctis Labyrinthus--at the west; the main section of roughly east-west-trending canyons in the center; and some irregular depressions which merge with the chaotic terrain further east... The main canyon extends... a distance of 2,400 km. Along this entire length the canyon... consist[s] of parallel canyons and chains of craters and graben... The canyons are widest and deepest in the central section... where three huge parallel troughs are each close to 200 km across... [In t]he two northernmost troughs, the Ophir and Candor Chasms... layered sequences, suggestive of cyclic sedimentation, are most common."

"[To the East,] the canyons consist of two main depressions, the relatively narrow Ganges Chasma to the north and a broad depression including the Eos and Capri Chasms to the south. Both depressions continue eastward into irregular areas of chaotic terrain."

"Faulting [related to the Tharsis bulge] appears to have played a key role in formation of the canyons... The [data] suggest that faulting and erosion proceeded simultaneously rather than succeeding each other, because erosional features, which could not have formed until after faulting started, are themselves cut by faults."

"In summary, many of the characteristics of the canyon can plausibly be explained by faulting, mass wasting, and the effects of groundwater. We are left, however, with two major unsolved problems: the origin of the layered sediments in the central section and the fate of the materials excavated to create the enormous void that the canyons represent."

Obviously, we do not know very much about Valles Marineris. If we intend to send astronauts to Candor Chasma for field exploration, we should have as detailed knowledge as possible of the area surrounding the field study area. Geology is much better understood when it is placed into a regional context. This is analogous to scientists' strong desire to see over the horizon at the two Viking landing sites.

2.2.2.3.4.1 1998 Launch

This launch focuses on areas that are primary targets for human missions to Mars.

2.2.2.3.4.1.1 Candor Chasma

Candor Chasma is the proposed landing site for the SIMM human landing. Therefore this is the most critical site to survey. The Mars Landing Site Catalog (1990) has sites number 22, 43, 54, 72 in this area. Carr suggested a penetrator mission for site #72 which is between Ophir and Candor Chasmas. Site 22 is located on Candor Mensa, a mesa within Candor Chasma. Site #43 and #54 are both within Candor Chasma with 43 being to the south.

2.2.2.3.4.1.2 Melas Chasma

Melas Chasma is directly south of Candor Chasma and is in the main portion of Valles Marineris. It will most likely be out of range of the first astronaut group, but this is a location that may be the site the astronauts on future missions explore.

2.2.2.3.4.2 2000 Launch

2.2.2.3.4.2.1 Noctis Labyrinthus

This is the chaotic zone that is at the top of Valles Marineris. It is the probable source of the massive amount of water that carved out this massive valley. This is the highest risk mission of the set that will probably result in early destruction of the rover. Nevertheless, it is of extreme importance in understanding the martian fluvial environment. The rover should land about 50 km away for the start of the chaotic terrain. It should then proceed as far as possible into the chaotic zone.

2.2.2.3.4.2.2 Capri Chasma/Eos Chasma

Capri and Eos Chasma are at the far eastern end of Valles Marineris and are listed as site number 74.

2.3.2 Exploration vehicle science equipment

2.3.2.1 Goal of SEV exploration

The goal of the Surface Exploration Vehicle (SEV) is to allow two of the scientists on the astronaut team to explore a larger area than just the immediate base site. The SEV should provide as complete a field laboratory as possible while still being easy to use. For the first excursion, the focus of the SEV is on-surface and near-surface geology with some work in exobiology. In addition to the equipment in and on the vehicle, several science stations will be deployed at locations that are deemed interesting and useful by the astronauts and scientists on Earth. For continuing SEV trips, the SEV will be upgraded and changed to allow for a variety of other experiments as well as extending the original suite.

2.3.2.2 Assumptions and limitations of the system

To get a feel for how these instruments work together while doing exploration geology requires an understanding of the vehicle's constraints. On each expedition, the SEV has a range of about 75 km. The cabin has a limited amount of space and weight to dedicate to lab equipment. For extra vehicular activity (EVA), the space suits will be able to support an astronaut for about 8 hours. It is important that the astronauts plan to do as much work as possible outside on each EVA due to the problem of loss of atmosphere from the SEV when an astronaut goes through the vehicle's airlock. It has been estimated that an astronaut can safely go up to 3.3 km from the support vehicle during an EVA(Ref. Boyd and Clark, 1992). In addition to time constraints, the astronauts will be restricted by the limited mobility of the Mars suits they will be wearing. In particular, the gloves will present a problem in the use of hand held field geology tools. For example, an astronaut will not be able to use any small buttons and switches without great difficulty. As this is just a brief summary, please refer to Volume 4 for details on the SEV and the Mars suit.

2.3.2.3 Manned Vs. Unmanned Discussion

The debate between manned and robotic exploration is a heated topic. Instead of arguing for one side or the other, our goal is to take advantage of both systems and use their strengths together. As McGreevy and Stoker (1991) put it, "planetary field science is constrained by limitations of both humans, requiring life support, and machines, lacking sufficient intelligence." Together they have much greater potential. There are some obvious cases where you would only send one half. For example, you would not send people just to take pictures from orbit. But for these missions, we make the assumption that humans will go to Mars. Looking at both aspects, we will try to develop a relationship between humans and machines that makes the scientists' expedition much more productive and enjoyable.

2.3.2.3.1 Strengths and weaknesses of humans

Traditionally, a person on an EVA is a "managed person". However, on Mars this is not possible due to the long communication delays. Therefore, we must expect to give humans more leverage and flexibility to make decisions while they are on the surface of Mars. With a year long mission, it is definitely the case that the astronauts will be able to do a large amount of EVA time without supervision from Earth.

There are two main advantages of a human being located at the site of exploration. The first is that humans are currently able to deal with a much higher flow of sensory data. From this data they are able to pick out the interesting features which they should explore. More importantly, when a person is able to directly manipulate and move around his or her environment, that person is able to build up a model of the world from which hypotheses can be constructed and tested.

The second advantage is the incredible strength of human dexterity and planning abilities. Once an astronaut has noticed an object that interests him, he is able to quickly walk over to it and do a quick examination. For example, when a geologist encounters an interesting outcrop of rock, he will probably smash off a sample, grab a chuck, and examine it up close. It would take a robot a long time to do these same tasks whether guided from Earth or running autonomously.

McGreevy and Stoker (1991) give a summary of what a geologist does in the field: "Geologic field work consists of highly integrated perceptual, cognitive, manipulative, and locomotion behaviors organized around a hierarchy of scientific goals and methods, and it is unlikely that automation and robotics will be able to replace this human capability any time soon. Thus, for missions beyond the mere rote gathering of rocks, that is, for planetary surface field work, human presence is required." The geologists they interviewed said, "'we smash a lot of rocks' to find a good sample." As a geologist explores, they "move through an environment and manipulate it at will, so as to come to understand it."

Another proponent of human exploration, Paul Spudis (1992), gives us some insight into what tasks humans are especially suited to over machines. He says that, "exploring a planet brings

out the best in people and the worst in machines." He names three areas at which humans excel: "installing complex instruments, replacing equipment, and doing field work." One example Spudis cites is particularly enlightening: Soviet Luna 15, 16, 20, 24 missions to the Moon show that coring is very difficult for robots to accomplish. No complete cores were returned from any of these missions. However, with the Apollo missions, three attempts to obtain cores were made. Despite many difficulties, all three return the full 8 ft core.

The ability to improvise and improve the current situation is an important human strength that is often seen in Antarctic exploration. One recent example is with NASA Ames' Telepresence Demonstration Project. While the group was in Antarctica this year, they discovered they had an opportunity to try a telepresence link from near McMurdo base to Ames Research Center; something they had not planned to do until a year later. While they were on the ice, their field engineer was able to reprogram part of the system to allow for this new capability. The flexibility of these people allowed them to pull off something that they were not capable of when they left for the ice.

Now that we have gone through the strengths of people doing exploration, let us take a quick look at what are the weaknesses of humans. The first problem is with the psychology of astronauts. These people are under a number of pressures: stress, danger, homesickness, and loneliness. These pressures can degrade the performance of a field scientist.

Secondly, there are some serious physical limitations of the human body. Every astronaut requires sleep and life support in order to stay alive. These requirements drive the development of any exploration system as can be seen with the SIMM habitat, SEV, and Mars suit which consume a major portion of the mass budget of the system.

Perhaps the greatest negative of a human presence on any expedition is the potential for loss of life. The US, in particular, is extremely upset at any loss of its astronauts, as evidenced by the explosion of the Shuttle Challenger. The loss of one of twenty micro rovers on a mission would undoubtedly be noted by the country, but would not cause a great public outcry.

2.3.2.3.2 Strengths and weaknesses of machines

There are a variety of advantages of robotic exploration. The most obvious is their ability to explore without the extra burdens that go along with a manned mission. The whole biological life support system can be left behind on Earth. Along the same lines, the structures and spaces required for human occupancy are not needed. This allows instruments to be sent to the same location as with humans, but with a much lower mass. The smaller size and complexity allow for dramatically cheaper missions.

Another set of advantages of robotics is that they can be made to be hardier than humans. It is possible to integrate radiation shielding and error correction to electronic components and structures that can be constructed of materials not susceptible to break down from radiation. A feature of machines not currently available in humans is the ability to switch off components and

hibernate. A lander could be programmed to sleep during the winter when solar power does not provide enough power to run the scientific instruments.

The last main set of benefits of machines is extremely useful to augment human capabilities while exploring. These are primarily things that humans can do, but machines can easily do better. An extremely simple example is a powered drill. It would take forever for an astronaut to hand crank a core into the surface, whereas a powered drill can get a core in a comparatively very short time. On the computational side, machines are much better at crunching numbers and keeping records. An astronaut could write on a map and field notes any observations and measurements made, but a computer in the form of a geographical information system (GIS) could record this information and provide virtually instant access of any stored information to astronauts on an EVA. This would provide a much better system that frees up the astronaut from clutter and lets him focus on field work rather than note taking. Machines can also augment the sensory capabilities of humans by, for example, providing imaging in parts of the spectrum not seen by human eyes.

A solo robot working out in the field has a completely different perspective while doing field work. A teleoperated vehicle, in the simplest form, may not retain any information of the area it traverses. On the other end of the spectrum, the most complex autonomous vehicle will have detailed terrain models and a variety of other information on board, but the robot has little or no understanding of that information. All of the scientific work is done by humans located elsewhere. The autonomous vehicle has to either rely on simple reactive controls or it has to have a large computation capability since planning and decision making are such tough computational tasks.

Another drawback of robotic exploration is the limited dexterity of automated actuators (grippers, tools, and such) as compared to the human hand. This greatly reduces the flexibility of these systems. For example, a human is able to do simple repairs such as replacing fuses without much trouble as seen with the repair of the Solar MAX satellite by replacing three blown fuses. However, a robotic system must rely on redundancy and the cleverness of Earth based operators to remain operational. An example of this is the Galileo high gain antenna which is stuck partially closed. Operators have tried all sorts of tactics and maneuvers to dislodge the stuck ribs to no avail. The robotic spacecraft is able to continue its mission due to the redundant design of including a second, low gain, antenna which is currently working. On a human mission, an astronaut would be sent on an EVA to open the ribs by hand.

2.3.2.4 Scientific Instrument Systems

This section is a set of proposed scientific systems to be placed on the SEV. Some are to run automatically, while others require the attention or even the full focus of an astronaut. No attempt has been made for all of the systems to distinguish which belongs in one or both of the SEVs or in the SEV trailer. It is assumed that the main base will have a much more complete lab setup than is possible on the SEVs.

2.3.2.4.1 Chemical reactants

There are a number of useful chemicals that will help with preparation and examination of samples collected. Some of the tasks that chemicals are used for are etching, determining the states of atoms and molecules and looking for life. Any container for reacting samples with chemicals needs to be able to be vented to the Martian atmosphere on command. This area needs further study, as it is not known how many chemicals will react in the martian environment. Some standard tests will not work under very different pressure and temperature ranges. For example, the common test for calcium carbonate is putting a few drops of HCl solution on a sample to see if it "fizzes." Under the low pressure, liquid HCl solution is going to go straight to a gas even if it is not in contact with calcium carbonate. There is always the possibility of an explosive reaction that was not expected. The reactants will have to be used sparingly and only on promising samples since they are generally not reusable.

2.3.2.4.2 Core drill

There should be a drill/coring device on the vehicle. The core device will be mounted on the SEV so the mass of the vehicle will provide the drilling counter mass. This system is much preferable to a poor astronaut trying to use one of these as evidenced by the struggles of the Apollo astronauts. It would be helpful for the drill to be operable from the inside of the SEV, but seems very impractical since core drills are very "hands on" tools. As on the Apollo missions, the core drill should have a replaceable sleeve to allow for easier removal and containment of the core. The preferred material for the sleeve should be determined once it is understood what materials will survive the martian environment.

It is important that the cores are labeled and oriented properly for numerous reasons. For example, if the cores' orientations are not carefully marked then any paleo-magnetism or paleocurrent readings on the cores will be almost entirely useless. However, it is assumed that not all cores will be returned to either the base and/or to Earth. Some cores may be photographed, sampled, and then simply discarded.

2.3.2.4.3 Deployable science stations

The deployable science stations are sets of instrument packages that are left at field sites of interest. Their primary instruments will be a seismometer and a meteorology system. Additional instruments will be attached as determined closer to launch time. The overall system will consist of support electronics, a solar panel, a 2 meter mast, and a 5 Watt VHF communications system to relay data through the Mars Areosynchronous Satellite (MACS). Deployment will consist of securing the main system and mast and then running a line to the seismometer a short distance away. The seismometer will be coupled to the ground with a 30 to 40 cm spike driven into the ground by an astronaut.

On each mission the deployed stations will be left in the field. When a SEV returns from each mission, it will be reloaded with new deployable stations. Since there are a larger number of

stations that can be carried on an expedition, they may be initially deployed in an area near the main base. This will allow for detailed initial characterization of the seismic noise and weather patterns in the area of the base. Once the stations are needed, they can be picked up and taken on expeditions.

The basic weight has not been carefully studied, but the stations should weigh less than fifteen kilograms each. Additionally, their weight will depend on what instruments are added to each unit on top of the basic design. They should be designed for a long duration lifespan so they can be used in conjunction with a number of different experiments and extend the global Mars network survey.

2.3.2.4.4 Scanning Electron microscope

A JPL study claimed that a scanning electron microscope(SEM) could be built that weighs only thirteen kilograms and consumes about 47 watts(Ref. SIMM Report, 1992). Since the weight of such a package is so low, it would be helpful to include a SEM in at least one of the SEVs or the trailer.

2.3.2.4.5 Elemental composition scanners

Elemental composition scanners can be used for biochemistry, chemistry, dating, and mineralogy. There are a large number of different systems available (XRF/XRD, APXS, GCMS, DSC/EGA, etc.) The system will be an extension of the work started by the Viking landers. A combination of composition scanners should be included, since each design is optimized to look at different sets of elements and compounds.

One possible setup, that has not as of yet been considered for use on Mars, would be to add the capability to date rock grains. This technique uses a laser to vaporize a series of individual grains. The Argon released is measured in a mass spectrometer for K/Ar dating. The biggest limiting factor is the power output of the laser required - to do effective dating, at least 5-7 watts, non-pulse is needed. Currently such technology is available in a size that is suitable for use in one of the SEVs or the SEV trailer, but it needs to be space qualified for use on Mars. Also, if as in several other proposed Mars missions, there is a nuclear reactor present, then it may be possible to do Ar40/Ar39 dating.

2.3.2.4.6 Field tools

Tables 2.3.2.4.6-1 and 2.3.2.4.6-2 (Ref. Boyd and Clark, 1992) summarize the basic field tools for use while on EVAs. Refer to Boyd and Clark (1992) for an excellent description of the field tool requirements. Additionally, a hefty sledge hammer for an initial seismic wave source and for generally mashing large rocks which is also for taking out aggressions on poor, hapless rocks.

Mapping	Analysis	Acquisition
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Mapping Board	Hand Lens	Rock Hammer
Laser Rangefinder	Hardness Tester	Tongs
Clinometer	Color Chart	Scoop
	Magnet	Sample Bags
	Element Analyze	Sample Containers
	Temperature Probe	Still Camera
	Video Camera	Gnomon

TABLE 2.3.2.4.6-1 FIELD PORTABLE TOOLS

Mapping (subsurface)	Analysis	Acquisition
Ground Penetrating Radar	X-ray Fluorescence	Coring Drill
Seismic	Multispectral Imaging	Core Drive Tubes
	Penetrometer	Shovel and Pick
	Sample Scale	Saw

TABLE 2.3.4.4.6.2 FIELD TRANSPORTABLE TOOLS

2.3.2.4.7 Gravimeter

The gravimeter is used to determine the density of local areas. The data collected by this device provides important background information to aid in the interpretation of various other instruments. In and of itself, it is useful for seeing things like the roots of mountains that project into the denser mantle and sections of dense mineral deposits, such as Fe ore deposits.

2.3.2.4.8 Ground Penetrating Radar

Ground penetrating radar (GPR) provides the fastest access to the top 80m of crust by reflecting a radar signal off of subsurface structures. GPR can serve several functions on a martian expedition. The most important is general stratigraphic data to help geological analysis. Along with geologic analysis is the search for ground ice and water. Large icy zones show up very distinctly in GPR data and provide an advantage in that they create a "window" that allows the radar signal to probe deeper into the strata. The only real drawback to this technique is the large volume of data produced and the computation time required to process the data. However, at the current rate at which computer systems are developing this will not be a major concern.

The SEV makes a strong base of operation for a GPR system. When the vehicle is stationary or moving very slowly, the system is able to "stack" multiple soundings to remove random noise

from the data. This is a very effective technique and is used extensively. While the vehicle is moving, the system will not be able to stack as many echoes but it will still be able to provide a good view of the subsurface. This has been proven with radars mounted on helicopters that are flown over glaciers and one van has been outfitted to survey roads.

Before construction of the base, the astronauts will have to survey the area for the best site on which to locate the habitat structure. A subsurface void that went unnoticed could pose a major hazard to the crew. Collapse of a ground void under the habitat would probably compromise the integrity of the many seals. The people in Florida who build their homes over limestone caves that collapsed to form sinkholes would probably concur that this is a major concern! A second problem, which is less dramatic, but still just as important is soil compaction. GPR can be used to make a three-dimensional survey of soil porosity so we can predict how the regolith will react to loading from structures. Therefore it is imperative that the SEV is used to make a detailed survey using GPR and its coring device to ensure the stability of the habitat.

The search for voids may possibly be extended to the moving SEV. If the SEV had its GPR antenna mounted on a boom out in front of the vehicle, the crew could monitor the GPR data real-time on a digital strip chart as they traverse unknown dangerous territory. It is not known how stable the martian surface is and this could be a major hazard for the crew. A system like this has not been tried but it is a strong possible application.

The most advanced GPR system in general use is the pulseEKKO III system made by a Canadian firm. It was developed under funding of the Canadian Geologic Survey. The pulseEKKO III has a total system weight of 22.25 kg and is carried around in a wheelbarrow. (Ref. Annan and Davis, 1992) This weight includes three antennas that cover 50, 100, and 200 MHz. This system does not use the latest in technology and is not an integrated system so a GPR system for martian exploration will most likely be in the 5 to 10 kg range for a much improved system. From the experience of field use of this system, it has been concluded that "GPR data provide ... excellent sedimentological information, which has been used to evaluate raw materials potential of different types of land forms." (Ref. Sutinen, 1992) Even using this system, it is possible to rapidly survey an area. For example, using this system carried by hand, a 8 km line was surveyed in about 6 hours (Ref. Dallimore and Davis, 1992).

GPR systems have already begun to show their value. From space shuttle based radar soundings, scientists were able to discover an underground river, roads, and a lost trading city. In the northern Canadian territories, GPR has been used to help understand massive ground ice and how it interacts with other rock units (Ref. Pilon, Allard, Seguin, 1992). And finally taking GPR up to high frequencies and ranges of several meters, it has been possible to detect fractures up a few millimeters thick within rock (Ref. Davis and Annan, 1992).

2.3.2.4.9 Meteorology station

To help characterize the local and global weather patterns, the SEV should have a barometer, a thermometer, an anemometer, and several photometers mounted on a roof mast that puts the instruments above the two meter surface layer.

2.3.2.4.10 Video Imaging System

The SEV's imaging system should consist of a multispectral camera system. The SEV crew will rely primarily on their vision for understanding the geology they are exploring. Therefore the imaging system is of critical importance to extending the astronauts abilities.

The camera should be mounted up high on a rooftop mast to give the best view of the SEV and surrounding areas. Together with a strong telescoping lens system, the astronauts will be able to gain a large amount of useful information about areas that they were only able to travel near, thereby greatly increasing the value of the SEV expeditions. The mast will allow the people inside the SEV to get a bird's eye view of any work they are doing with the robotic manipulators that are mounted on the front of the vehicle.

There are two choices for the imaging. The first is a binocular system, which allows for the SEV to be easily used in a telepresence mode when desired. Range information can be calculated by comparing the location of an object in both images, which can be done automatically by the on-board computer. The monocular system's main advantage is that it provides a savings in weight and complexity. A monocular system is still usable for telepresence but may be more fatiguing to the human operator.

A laser range finder running in parallel with the video camera(s) is extremely important. This will allow the SEV crew to quickly build up a high resolution geologic map containing the location of the data or observations taken. The laser range finder will also allow distances to be overlaid on images of the terrain to assist the SEV crew in planning their route over the martian surface and help them to keep in their size perspective straight in this foreign world.

2.3.2.4.11 Organic chemistry analysis/life detection

See section 2.3.1 for discussion of the search for life from the SEV and what systems will be required.

There is one major concern with doing searches for organic molecules from the SEV that needs to be considered. The presence of humans inherently contaminates almost every surface of the SEV with organic contaminants: from single molecules, cells, and bacteria and small critters. This is a major concern which must be addressed but it does not preclude trying to do these kinds of experiments, just that caution should be used in interpreting these results.

2.3.2.4.12 Petrographic and stereo microscopes

The petrographic microscope is the geologist's mainstay for laboratory analysis of samples. Petrographic work can provide information on mineralogy, grain size, porosity, weathering and

transport processes, cementing, and microfossils. It is essentially a standard binocular lab microscope with polarizing filters and an attached video camera. It should be smaller than 1 cu. ft.

2.3.2.4.13 Sample preparation tools

In order to get a better look at many of the samples collected, the astronauts will have to prepare the samples by a number of means. This will allow a larger number of samples to be studied at Mars. This is especially important for facilitating better selection of samples for return to Earth, since the return payload is very limited.

The petrographic microscope is used to look at the light transmitted through a "thin section" of a rock. In order for this technique to work, the samples must be ground down and finally polished to a 30 to 40 micron thickness. The first step in this process is to use a rock saw (basically a diamond saw or equivalent) to cut a sample down to about 1.5 x 3 x .5 cm block. This saw is also listed as one of the field tools. It will most likely require a cooling system if it is operated within the SEV lab area, but it should not be used inside the SEV due to the dust and general mess that it would create. If the SEV's atmosphere reacts with the samples, then most of the samples will have to remain within the sample boxes in a Mars atmosphere.

2.3.2.4.14 Seismic pulse source

There are four ways to image the subsurface of a planetary body: gravity, resistance, dielectric, and acoustic waves. We have already described systems for gravity and dielectric (GPR) measurements. One of the most commonly used on Earth is acoustic seismic soundings. With this technique it is possible to get structure with the reflection data and rock type with the velocity data.

Noise is one of the major impediments to getting good seismic data. There are several sources of noise in the Earth. The worst problem is with people and traffic. Crews usually have to do their work at night to reduce this problem. On Mars, the only human source of noise is from the operations of the base and the six astronauts so this is not a big concern on Mars. A global source of noise on Earth is the oscillations of the oceans. It is 7 to 14 Hz noise that is even detectable in the highlands of Tibet. Again, there are no oceans on Mars and the tidal effects of the Phobos and Demos are very tiny. A final big problem is with wind. It is especially prevalent if a detector is only laying on the surface and not on a spike or buried. Wind should be the only big problem for Mars. Even this problem is greatly reduced by the lower atmospheric pressure. Due to the lower pressure, the wind on Mars will exert a force equal to that experienced on Earth with a wind that is approximately 10% of the Martian wind speed. Therefore, on Mars the biggest limiting factors are the number and quality of the detectors and the strength and control of the seismic sources.

In addition to the network of seismic detectors that should be in place from a variety of Mars precursor missions, the SEV will lay its own set of detectors. The primary detectors will be a line

of geophones that are deployed and retrieved from an SEV. Optimally, on Earth, a crew will lay a cable of 120 detectors over 6 km. The geophones weigh a few pounds each. The cable weighs about 60 lb. for 500 meters. (Ref. Klemperer, 1993). This is not a realistic system for use on Mars. Another option is to lay out boxes containing a geophone and a timer. The timer will turn on the device at a time just before the test and store the data. After the sounding is done, the devices are then picked up and the data is downloaded to the SEV. In addition to the string of geophones, the seismic profiles will rely heavily on the stations deployed from the SEV on excursions which are equipped with high quality seismometers. In order to keep all of these instruments exactly synced up, the MACS satellite needs to provide a timing signal to all of the seismic stations and the SEV.

There are a several choices for seismic source pulses. The simplest method is to hit a spike into the ground with a good sized sledge hammer. This is very cheap and easy, but is only able to sense about 100 meters below the surface. This is the system that will be used on the first SEV excursion. The next level up in imaging ability is a weight drop system. The SEV will drop a large mass of about 100 kilograms from a height of a meter or two. On Earth, the drop tube is pumped down to a low pressure. The atmospheric pressure on Mars is low enough that there should be very little drag on the falling mass. Unfortunately, the lower gravity will give the falling weight much less energy. This system can be augmented with an electromagnetic accelerator if there is enough power available on future SEVs.

There are two additional methods which are much harder to do on Mars but have a much greater ability to image deep within the martian crust. These are "Vibroseis" and explosives. Vibroseis involves vibrating an entire vehicle on a pad at a variety of frequencies between 8 and 40 Hz. The problem with explosive charges is that the charges have to be placed at least 5 to 10 meters below the surface and the explosives are a heavy expendable. These two systems are able to image to much greater depths: a 50 kg shot on Earth can image up to 70 km down into the Earth's crust. With much larger shots, it is possible to image up to about 200 km horizontally.

Finally, Mars itself provides a fantastic and free seismic source to image the internal structure of the planet: marsquakes. This should be a focus more for non-human missions.

The initial system will consist of about 10 to 20 geophones and the source which will be a sledge hammer struck on a stake. The sounding will only attempt to image the top 100 meters of the surface. As the human missions to Mars continue, more geophone units will be brought to strengthen the line. Additionally, a weight drop system will be added to one of the vehicles to provide an improved seismic source.

A.1 Rover Technology

A.1.0 Autonomous Rovers

A.1.1 Introduction

It is important that we take an overview look at all of the rover technology currently available. There are currently a variety of systems that are near to being ready to fly and many other systems that present prototype implementations of concepts that could be a big improvement in our ability explore the surfaces of other planets. The cost savings of using pre existing technologies and systems can be tremendous. As John Garvey of McDonnell Douglas said, "Our Russian colleagues have developed true world-class capabilities in planetary exploration. Working with them, we can do better work than we could alone." (Ref. Wildermuth, 1993)

There are currently two camps of robotics that tend to argue back and forth along the major division in this field: simple, small "micro-rovers" versus larger more complicated rovers. There are definite trade offs between the two design approaches. I will cover both types of rovers and will present a concept for a combined mission that tries to use different scales of rovers to make a more robust system. Using micro rovers could send a large number of small micro-rovers in the space and weight required for one or two regular rovers to Mars. There would be less concern over losing a percentage of micro rovers compared to losing one of 1 or 2 larger rovers. On the other hand, a single larger rover can have more onboard computational power and larger scientific instruments.

There is also the split between legged vehicles, wheeled vehicles, and vehicles that integrate the two paradigms. Legs provide a more stable platform for instruments, are more energy efficient for motion, and cause less environmental damage to the area explored, but they require higher computational loads in order to figure out where to place each foot. Wheeled vehicles are mechanically simpler, computationally less expensive and more reliable (?), but require more power for moving the same distance and leave behind wheel tracks.

A.1.2 Mission Ready Rovers

A.1.2.1 Flown Rovers

So far, only the Soviet Union has attempted to land robotic rovers on other planets or moons. They have sent a total of 5 rovers, of which two were successfully operated. The fifth, which is not described here, is a hopping rover (PROP-F) sent on the ill fated Phobos 2 mission. In addition to the work in rovers presented here, any serious design work on planetary exploration vehicles should look at the Apollo Lunar Roving Vehicle (LRV). The LRV will not be covered here because it had to be driven by an astronaut. The remote piloting system was scrapped in the concept phase due to weight constraints.

LRV Picture 1

LRV Picture 2

A.1.2.1.1 Lunokhod 1 & 2

The first planetary rover, Lunokhod I (Moon Rover 1), landed on the Moon November 17, 1970 and explored the moon for 11 months. The Lunokhod's total mass was 750 kilograms, with the 105 kg undercarriage moving the rover along at 0.8 to 2 kph. (Ref. Kermurjian, 1990) Lunokhod 2 arrived on the Moon on January 16, 1973. The two Lunokhods operated for a total of 414 days and traveled 7 and 37 kilometers. The Lunokhod design has eight wheels and is powered by solar with a storage battery.

A.1.2.1.2 Mars 2 & 3

The first and only two robotic rovers reached the surface of Mars in 1971 during the Soviet Mars 2 and 3 missions. The Mars 2 lander reached the surface on November 27 followed by Mars 3 on December 2. The two landers arrived during the worst martian dust storm on record and both of the landers failed: Mars 2 crashing into the surface and Mars 3 lasting a brief 20 seconds on the surface. As a result, the two rovers never got a chance to operate. These two small rovers were designed to walk 15 meters on skis while carrying two instruments each: a dynamic penetrator and a densitometer. (Ref. Kermurjian, 1990)

A.1.2.2 Currently Flyable Rovers

These rovers are very close to the point where they can be sent on missions and are slated for missions in the near future.

A.1.2.2.1 Marsokhod

Figure A.1.2.2.1-1

The Marsokhod (Russian for "Mars Rover") was developed through several iterations at VNIITransmash (Ref. Kermurjian et al., 1992). The Marsokhod is pictured in Figure A.1.2.1-1. The result of this research is the very capable Small Marsokhod (TABLE A.1.2.1-1) that is scheduled to fly on the Russian Mars 96 mission (See Section 2.2.2.3.2). In addition, while the Russian design team was working in California they quoted a price for the Marsokhod: \$60 M - delivered to the surface of Mars with an instrument package provided by the purchaser. The rover has been successfully tested in the California deserts: Dumont Dunes north of Baker and Mars Hill in Death Valley (Ref. Anderson, 1992) as well as in several laboratory sand boxes and in the volcanic terrain of Kamchatka.

Price per Unit: \$60M (delivered to martian surface) Total Mass: 100 kg Life-Time: 1 Terrestrial Year Covered Distance Goals: 100 km/Year, 50 to 100m/Day Velocity: <180m/h Electrical Power: 10 to 20W (RTG) Chassis: 31 kg Articulated Frame with 6 cone wheels, by Vniitransmach Payload: 14.5 kg (8 kg science + drilling system) Width: 60 cm Length: 90 cm (Ref. Runavot, 1993; JPL Universe, 1993) The Marsokhod 96 Table A.1.2.2.1-1

A.1.2.2.2 Rocky IV

Figure A.1.2.2.2-1

JPL's Rocky IV micro-rover (Figure A.1.2.2.2-2) is an excellent expression of the drive to develop cheaper methods for exploring planetary surfaces. It fits well into NASA's Discovery Class Missions discussed previously in that it focuses on simplifying difficult engineering tasks: "...[M]any complex tasks may [be] achieved by programming a robot with a set of behaviors and activating or deactivating a subset of those behaviors as required by the specific situation in which the robot finds itself... Behavior control requires much less computation than is required by traditional AI planning techniques. The reduced computational requirements allow the entire rover to be scaled down to the micro-rover (1-5 kg) level." Rocky is meant to operate autonomously on small tasks with little communication between Earth and the rover. The behavior system also has the advantage of working well in a team of micro-rovers. The benefits of this system should be "savings in fabrication costs, launch mass, landing mass, and increased mission reliability." (Ref. Miller, 1990)

The two main problems with this small of a vehicle are 1) the communication systems and many of the instruments do not scale down well with the rest of the rover and 2) with this design philosophy, this vehicle is not usable for telepresence operations. The scaling problems can be solved by sending multiple rovers, each with a different set of science instruments, and by relaying the rovers data through a single uplink station on the surface of Mars.

For a recent press demonstration, the JPL prototype weighed in at 7 Kg and is 61 cm long by 38.5 cm wide by 36 cm high. It has six 13- centimeter (5-inch) diameter wheels made of strips of stainless steel foil with cleats to provide traction. Rocky runs on 5 watts of solar energy, used during the day. At night, the electronics are turned off, and the keep-alive batteries run the unit. Rocky was controlled by a Macintosh PowerBook for the demo. Rocky is able to ascend slopes of 26°. It is equipped with a visible infrared spectrometer, a color camera, a rock chipper, and a soft-sand scoop that takes soil samples. Additionally, the rover can place a seismometer on the surface (Ref. JPL Universe, 1993). The control system is based on the subsumption architecture of Brooks, known as behavior-based control. The system currently runs on a tiny 1-MIP Motorola 6811 microcontroller with 40k of memory (Ref. Gat et al., 1993.) A space-qualifiable version of Rocky IV scaled to approximately 4 kg is currently being designed for a planned 1996 MESUR Pathfinder launch (See Section 2.2.2.3.4).

Price per unit	\$2.5M (includes landing system)
Total Mass	7.5 kg
Life-Time	7 Days (minimum)
Coverage Distance Goals	100 m
Velocity	~1 m/min.
Electrical Power	100W Hr/Day (Solar) + 150 W Hr non-rechargeable battery
Chassis	Rocker/Bogie 6 wheel system
Power Consumption	14.7 W Hr/Day; 8.0 W Hr/Night

(Ref. Reynolds, 1993) 1996 JPL Rocky IV

Table A.1.2.2.2-1

A.1.3 Development Platforms

A.1.3.1 Ambler

Ambler is a large prototype rover developed at Carnegie Mellon University. It is supported by six legs and weighs 2500 kg. Ambler is equipped with large on board computational facilities and

has shown an ability to traverse a wide variety of terrains including slopes up to 30° while using a laser scanner to image the landscape (Ref. Krotkov and Simmons, 1992).

Mass	2500 kg
Height	4.1 to 6.0 m
Width	4.5 to 7.1 m
Locomotion	6 legs - circulating gate
Speed	35 cm/min.
Power Consumption	
Steady-State	1400 W
Laser Scanner	+210 W
Leg Motion	+150 W
Horizontal Body Motion	+600 W
Vertical Body Motion	+1800 W

Ambler

Table A.1.3.1-1

A.1.3.1.1 SITE-Recon Mission

Why An Ambler Mk 2 on the SITE-Recon Mission?

Code named: "Bullwinkle"

The SITE-Recon mission proposed in Section 2.2.2.5 is based on a modified cargo vehicle. The mission as whole is meant to demonstrate working versions of a number of untested systems by sending them on a useful Mars precursor mission. In particular, the mission contains an unusual array of robotic rovers. The mission proposes two groups of rovers: 1) 10 Marsokhod Rovers and 2) one second generation Ambler rover (named "Bullwinkle") that is parent to 10 Rocky micro rovers. The driving force behind this assortment of rovers is that we do not know what the "best rover configuration is so we must try a number of different combinations in actual field use to gain more hands-on experience.

The primary reason for the choice was the large amount of local computational power available on the Ambler (currently two Sun workstations) that allow the Ambler and subordinate rovers to be almost entirely autonomous short of deciding the high level mission goals. This is important, in that the mission design already has ten Marsokhod rovers which use extensive human interaction to perform their missions.

A large part of this mission is a technology demonstration. The combination of ten Rocky IV rovers and an Ambler allow for complicated grouping behaviors to be tested. This will increase the useability of the group without having complex computational facilities located on each and every rover. See Gat's paper (Ref. Miller, 1990) for more detailed description of grouping behaviors in simple/small rovers. The group behaviors can be implemented with simple high level commands from the Ambler which is a base that provides a communication base/beacon/repeater with an antenna that is high enough up that it should be visible by most of the group at any time. The Ambler will be able to carry one large communications system that will allow the group to communicate back to the mother ship (the cargo vehicle) over a much longer ground distance with higher data rates.

The taller Ambler will allow us to mount a meteorology station above the surface layer and take this station a good distance from the landing site. Along with this meteorology station will go a nice imaging system. As Professor Don Lowe of Stanford University has said, a lot of excellent geology can be done with good, high resolution imaging with a zoom lens. If we were able to mount such an imaging system so high above the martian surface and be amble to move it around, we would be able to explore areas a long way away from the roving group without actually having gone to these sites.

It is assumed that the Ambler will have a much larger range than the Marsokhod. As the Ambler makes its traverse, it serves at a refueling depot for its daughter rovers (i.e.. recharging of batteries). This extends the effective use of the Rocky rovers.

Finally, the mission already contains ten Marsokhods, which only use up a small portion of the available 4000 kg payload available on the cargo vehicle. It would be silly to propose that we send another ten to the same area when we have an opportunity to test other systems. Admittedly, a sample return vehicle would probably fit nicely in this space/weight, but this would be a repetition of many previous proposals - numerous authors have discussed a variety of sample return missions. We need to try out some new ideas and get creativity flowing. This is an excellent opportunity to combine two different rover methodologies and do lots of science at the same time.

A.1.3.2 Attila

MIT Attila

Attila is a small prototype developed by Rodney Brooks and Colin Angle at MIT . It is a continuation of the initial "insect" rovers concept. The little bugger has 6 legs and a small video camera. In addition to Attila, Brooks has developed another insect like microrobot known as Genghis. The ISX Corporation, which works with Brooks, had ISRobotics build a more robust, environmentally sealed, tracked micro rover known as Pebbles that is equipped with a soil scoop.

At the 1992 California desert rover tests, a ramp was added to the Russian Marsokhod rover so Attila and Pebbles could ride piggyback on the Marsokhod (Ref. Bullock, 1993.) The idea was to provide a smaller vehicle that could carry a sampling tool into tight areas and also as an extra set of eyes should the parent rover get stuck. This is very similar to the SIMM '93 SITE-Recon mission concept (See Section 2.2.2).

A.1.3.3 Dante-Virgil

Dante was an attempt to robotically go where man has been unable to go: the throat of the active Mt. Erebus volcano in Antarctica. Dante's goal was to climb into the caldera and sample the active lava lake. Two previous attempts have been made by a combined New Zealand, French and American team in 1974 and '78. The first attempt was aborted on the caldera rim and the second attempt was halted within 30m of the floor when the scientist being lowered by rope was nearly killed in an eruption. The vehicle was to be delivered to the edge of the caldera by a turbine driven vehicle named Virgil. Once Dante was let off of Virgil, it was to repel by a tether mounted on Virgil down the lava lake to take samples of the lava's composition. Unfortunately, Dante failed 21 feet below the caldera rim. The fiber optic communications link between Dante and Virgil broke leaving Virgil immobile. Due to this failure, the project was called off and Dante was rescued from the cliff. It was predicted that Dante would take 24 to 36 hours to descend 850 feet to the crater floor.

Amazingly, the vehicle was designed, built, and deployed in only a year. The vehicle has eight legs, weighs 450 kg and is 1.8m x 2.5m x 3m in size. The complete system consisted of four nodes: Dante, Virgil, Base Station (Erebus Hut), and Mission Control (NASA Goddard Space Flight Center) Dante's journey was computationally expensive: it used a total of 5 sun4 and 3 Motorola 68030 VME computers throughout the system. See Table A.1.3.3-1 for more of the vehicle parameters.

The project was led by William "Red" Whittiker of the Field Robotics Center, Carnegie Mellon University who planned and executed the project. The project was also co-lead by Philip R. Kyle of the New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology. Dante is a synthesis of the previous work done at CMU on the NavLab and Ambler projects. "The robot demonstration project had three objectives: to test telerobotic capabilities; to test the use of such sophisticated hardware in a very harsh and demanding environment; and to test the use of advanced computer programs which would enable machines such as the Dante robot to act under a form of machine

intelligence." The development and telepresence aspects of the process were considered a success despite the projects failure to reach the caldera floor and David Lavery, NASA Telerobotics program manager for the project feels "[t]he prototypes are worthy contenders for inclusion in any further planetary exploration."

Dante	
Propulsion	4 legs on each of 2 frames
Height	2.5 m
Width	1.875 m (foot to foot)
Length	3 m (foot to foot)
Ground Clearance	0 to 1.45 m
Speed	2 m/min.
Slope Handling	30° without tether
Telemetry	400 m fiber optic (in tether)
Power	Virgil via tether
Virgil	
Height	1 m
Width	1.2 m
Length	4 m
Weight	4540 kg
Speed	30 kph
Track	2.6 m
Ground Clearance	0.1 to 0.4 m
Power	Internal combustion engine & 5 kW Honda generator

Dante-Virgil
TABLE A.1.3.3-1

A.1.3.4 Robby

Robby comes out of work in the late '70's and early '80's on the Surveyor Lunar Rover Vehicle (SLRV). JPL combined its experience with the SLRV and the missions requirements for NASA's (now defunct) Mars Rover Sample Return (MRSR) program to develop the Robby testbed in 1988. Robby has been used to test planning algorithms, in particular they have focused on the "Semi Autonomous Navigation" (SAN) algorithm. In September, 1990, Robby successfully navigated a 100 m course in 4.3 hours (Ref. Wilcox et al., 1992). Robby has also been used as a platform to test sampling arms and algorithms (Ref. Cameron et al., 1992).

Robby is rather large: 3 segments, for a total of about 4 meters long and 2 meters with; six wheels, 1 meter in diameter each. It weighs 1200 Kg. Robby's design is able to surmount obstacles 50% larger than the wheel diameter.

A.1.3.5 Others

Obviously, there is much more out there than has been covered. A number of rover projects that the reader should be aware of: JPL's lab beast Tooth (Ref. Gat et. al., 1992), JPL's tiny Go-For: (Ref. Wilcox, 1992), MIT's MITY 1 & 2, plus many others. Also, do not forget all the work being done with submersible ROVs and AUVs - a rapidly developing industry that is doing large amounts of R&D. For example, see Section A.1.4.2 on telepresence ROV's.

A.1.4 Virtual Reality

Virtual Reality WWWeb Sites Virtual Reality (VR): "Virtual Reality deals with convincing the participant that s/he is actually in another place, by replacing the normal sensory input received by the participant with information produced by a computer. This is usually done through three-dimensional graphics and I/O devices which closely resemble the participant's normal interface to the physical world. The most common I/O devices are gloves, which transmit information about the participant's hand (position, orientation, and finger bend angles), and head-mounted displays, which give the user a stereoscopic view of the virtual world via two computer-controlled display screens, as well as providing something to mount a position/orientation sensor on." (Ref. sci.virtual-worlds, 1992)

A.1.4.1 Introduction

As computers and their tasks become more complicated and overwhelming, it is important to work on methods that make communicating and interacting with these machines a more natural affair. In the last ten years, it has become possible to interact with systems in new ways such as by the use of hand gestures and voice commands (Ref. Fisher et al., 1986). LCD glasses and head-mounted-displays (HMDs) allow the user to truly experience a three dimensional world instead of the prevalent 2D computer screen. In addition to visual and visceral immersion, three-dimensional auditory displays are another important aspect (Ref. Wenzel et al., 1988) which will allow the system to provide additional information without interfering with the users vision. A good overview of the technologies currently in use to generate virtual realities is written by Foley (1986) and the best introduction to virtual reality was written recently by a NASA Ames researcher (Ref. Ellis, 1991). All of these new technological advances come together to produce

some very interesting possibilities for planetary exploration that will affect everything from the way an astronaut will work on the surface of another planet to the average citizen who will get to explore the worlds created by orbiters, rovers, and astronauts.

The general population has a strange view of virtual reality . This comes from seeing such things as the Hollywood movie "Lawnmower Man." When asked about VR, they often bring up things like cyberpunks, "virtual sex" and Star Trek the Next Generation's "Holodeck." This does not have much of a relation to the current technology. It is important to clear your mind of the tremendous hype while thinking about what it can do for planetary exploration.

However, despite being way out of our technological reach, the Holodeck does bring in the right feeling of what virtual reality is about. In a number of episodes the crew of the Enterprise explore copies of the real world. It allows them a deeper view of a situation or a system. The Holodeck is very similar to and must have come from "the Cave" - an MIT project that surrounds a person in a room that has screens on all surfaces, thereby immersing the person in the environment projected by the video screens. A good example of the power of this immersion can be experienced at such places as the Disney Epcot Center's theater in the round. This is essentially a large circular auditorium that has movie screens completely surrounding the audience. This total immersion has a much greater power to instill the immensity of such things as the Grand Canyon as a simple flat screen could. The audience feels like they are there, because everywhere they turn is still the Grand Canyon. As the film drops into the canyon, the standing audience has to grab hand railings for balance since optic righting reflexes are stimulated. The goal is to make the person feel like they are really there.

A.1.4.2 Telepresence

Telepresence: "Telepresence is a high fidelity form of remote control in which the natural sensory capabilities of the human operator are projected through a robot to a distant work site." (Ref. Gwynne et al., 1992)

Geologists have said that, "The complex yet subtle nature of geological materials requires powers of observation, pattern recognition, and synthesis not possessed by automated devices. Field study...absolutely requires human geologists to be involved intimately." Telepresence technology provides us a way to get the scientists deeply involved in their field areas even when they are out of human reach, but we must be careful in applying telepresence: "if the remote operation becomes too cumbersome...the operator will concentrate more on mechanical aspects of the work and less on the intellectual ones" (Ref. Taylor and Spudis, 1989).

Rudimentary telepresence is achievable using only limited computational power. For example, the Telepresence Demonstration Project at NASA Ames achieved usable telepresence with their remotely piloted submersible using a simple Motorola 68000 based Commodore Amiga system (Ref. Schwehr, 1992). Unfortunately, most planetary exploration applications will need more computational power and more complex programs to function up to expectations. Using this

platform, the group has shown that telepresence can be an effective tool for scientific exploration.

NASA Ames TROV in Antarctica.

The Telepresence Demonstration Project, run by C.R. Stoker, used a submersible remotely operated vehicle (ROV), a Deep Ocean Engineering SuperPhantom II, as a development platform. The group added a head tracked camera and science instruments to the ROV for an initial testbed. The vehicle was operated successfully in several very different environments: a coral reef in the Florida Keys, the south shore of Lake Tahoe, and the ice covered Lake Hoare of the Antarctic Dry valleys. The trip to Antarctica is the most important of these expeditions because according to C.R. Stoker, "Antarctica is the most Mars-like environment on Earth." (Ref. NASA PR 92-147) The ROV is a big win for the group in allowing scientists to get around physiological constraints of diving, thus allowing the scientists to spend more time exploring their field areas. This is very similar to the constraints on astronauts due to life support systems. The telepresence system of the ROV succeeded in helping to improve the pilot's situation awareness while exploring underwater. In all three cases the vehicle was restricted to being less than 1100 from the pilot at the control console.

While the ROV was in Antarctica, the software was extended on the ice by a brilliant field engineer to allow for an operator to control the ROV from Ames while the vehicle dived under the ice near McMurdo base. The test was the first success of direct telepresence via satellite

link. In December, 1992, the CMU Dante robot used this same satellite link to control the robot on Mt. Erebus from state side.

Recently, Butler Hine's group at NASA Ames conducted further remote tests with a Marsokhod Rover located in Moscow at the IKI laboratory (Ref. NASA PR 93-84). The tests were designed to verify this technology for use on the Russian Mars 96 mission. Hine describes the control system at NASA Ames as "a 'tele-operator interface' because it is a combination of virtual reality and telepresence. We can drive the vehicle by looking through the rover's cameras, which is telepresence. We also can drive it using a computer-generated graphic simulation, which is virtual reality."

The time delay in response of the telepresence system for all of these tests was between 1/3 of a second for direct control up to a few seconds for telepresence via satellite. These results show that for on-sight or "on planet" situations, straight telepresence control of a vehicle or other robotic system works quite well, but there are several reasons to want to add layers between the operator and the machine. The most dramatic reason is for teleoperation of robotic explorers on other planets from Earth. For example, the distance between the Earth and Mars causes round trip delays of 11 min. 20 sec to 40 min. 50 sec depending on the positions of the two planets. With time delays of more than a few seconds, direct telepresence becomes more of a detriment and will cause the operator to quickly become fatigued (and damn bored!) The solution is to use predictive systems that model the environment and allow an operator to control a computer generated rover that acts like the real thing without the delay. The operator can then run through a series of operations with the model and then wait for the confirmation that the rover has achieved this set of goals. Predictive systems are currently being developed at NASA Ames in Hine and McGreevys' groups and in Schenker's Man-Machine Systems Group at JPL.

Another reason for wanting virtual reality between the operator and the vehicle is to allow the person to work through several different scenarios to see the simulated results of each. Once he decides on the proper sequence of events, the operator can move through the sequence with confidence or have the simulator send off the correct actions of the operator that were generated and saved during the tests.

"One can integrate and automate many of the vehicle functions that are normally driven manually. Teleoperation may thus be raised to a supervisory level, relieving the operator of tedious tasks such as piloting the vehicle from point-to-point. Automated control may be employed at the operator's discretion to free him of tiring tasks that range from the most mundane to the most complicated." (Ref. Gwynne et al., 1992) An excellent example comes from a joint project between Stanford's Aerospace Robotics Laboratory (ARL) and the Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute (MBARI), which is developing technologies for use on several different remotely operated submersible vehicles. The goal of their project is to design task level controls that are off-loaded onto local computers which should free the operator to focus more on planning and decision making than on the difficulties of piloting a vehicle. The group has developed "and demonstrated the capability of combined camera and vehicle tracking of

underwater targets" - i.e., the group created a system that can autonomously follow objects (such as a plastic turtle or a fish) as they move through the water. (Ref. Marks et al, 1992). When integrated with the MBARI ROV, this system should make following fish for hours on end a much more pleasant task for the ROV crew - allowing the scientist to keep following a fish without the highly experienced pilot always having to run the show.

McGreevy and Stoker (1991) conclude that "geologic field work consists of highly integrated perceptual, cognitive, manipulative, and locomotive behaviors organized around a hierarchy of scientific goals and methods, and it is unlikely that automation and robotics will be able to replace this human capability any time soon. Thus, for missions beyond the mere rote gathering of rocks, that is, for planetary surface field work, human presence is required. To effectively explore large areas of Mars or other terrestrial bodies, telepresence offers the best combination of man and machine."

A.1.4.3 Virtual Environments and Geographic Information Systems

While the various rovers sent to Mars are out exploring, they will return a large quantity of data that will have a 3-D base. A good way to store the data would be in a geographical information system (GIS) that allows data to be associated with the location at which it was collected. Once these data sets are put into the GIS along with the topographic data from the Mars Observer orbiter, it can be accessed with traditional database tools and directly from a virtual environment interface.

As these massive databases continue to expand we need a good way to explore this model of Mars. Virtual environments (VEs) are the creation, in virtual reality, of physical locations using a variety of data sets. At the moment we have Viking and soon to come is the Mars Observer Data sets with which to create a virtual Mars to explore. An immersive interactive environment will allow scientists to explore Mars and get the best intuitive/visceral feel for the planet. It will also be valuable in getting astronauts intimately acquainted with the geologic setting before they even leave for Mars. They will be able to explore any part of Mars anytime through the trip to re-explore any location.

Geologists like to have an oblique view of an area - i.e. like from a plane. "[The geologists] confessed to relying heavily on vision; theirs is a highly spatial business" say McGreevy and Stoker (1991). A VE can provide a close equivalent to a plane for the astronauts. The simulation will let them be able to quickly see from any angle they choose, even those not physically possible (like inside a mountain!)

A Marssuit heads up VR display can present the astronaut with terrain (topos), reference material, orbital photos while he is in the field. Similar systems have frequently been proposed for use in the zero-G environment around the space station Freedom (Ref. Fisher et al, 1988) as an EVA Spacesuit visor display. This system will allow easy hand-free note taking that is linked to the astronaut's location. The main impediment, speech recognition, should be up to speed by mission time.

Virtual Environment Work Station, by Scott Fisher, NASA Ames, 1990.

A system similar to a “Dataglove” (Ref. Fisher, 1986) can be integrated into the suit to allow an astronaut to more easily interact with a virtual reality system. This system would sense the position and orientation of the astronaut’s arms, hands, and fingers. A system like this would be lightweight and very trim (not bulky) with the use of small fiber optic flex sensors (patented by [VPL Research, Inc.](#))

A.1.4.4 Entertainment

While the astronauts are trapped in a small SEV and base, VR can provide an entertainment system with games and a way to tour Earth. Already, there have been attempts to commercialize virtual reality. In the game seen there are the BattleTech and Dactyl Nightmare games that involve groups of people battling it out in a virtual world. On a more benign level, the Diaspar Virtual Reality Network has attempted to set up an educational/entertainment system called "The Lunar Tele-operation Model One (LTM1)." It is supposed to be a model of a lunar base which people can connect to with their personal computers. Once connected they are able to interact with this simulated world and control model vehicles. An interesting idea, eh?

A.1.4.5 Conclusion

The technologies of virtual reality are presently at a point where they can be useful right now in planetary exploration as well as becoming more mature and refined in the future. By the time they become incorporated into the actual first manned mission to Mars they should be a very sophisticated and integral part of the mission operations. An example of the readiness of these technologies is that a telepresence system should be operational and used for the Mars 96 mission. Also there exist proposals for analyzing the Mars Observer data that will soon be available within a virtual reality setting. In the submersible industry, there is currently work on integrating virtual reality and telepresence into several ROV's and AUV's (untethered vehicles) at several locations. On the military side, a system known as Simnet is a simulation system built by BBN for training of military skills in tanks, helicopters, and other vehicles. It uses a combination of networked graphics displayed in physical mockups of the vehicles. There is also the wide variety of flight simulators for commercial and military use that rely on many of the same technologies.